

**o-ALDEHYDO-CARBOXYLIC ACIDS. PART III. A SYNTHESIS
OF 4:5 METHYLENEDIOXYPHTHALALDEHYDIC ACID
AND NEW SYNTHESSES OF 4- AND 5-METHOXY-
PHTHALALDEHYDIC ACIDS.**

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4:5-Methylenedioxyphthalaldehydic acid (V), for the synthesis of which an unsuccessful attempt was made by Stevens and Robertson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927 2791) has been synthesised by us by methods similar to those employed in the case of the opianic acids (Chakravarti and Swaminathan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 715, 873).

4:5-Methylenedioxyhomophthalic acid (I), prepared by the hydrolysis of 4:5-methylenedioxy-2-carboxyphenylacetonitrile (Edwards, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 817) has been oxidised in boiling xylene solution by means of selenium dioxide to 4:5-methylenedioxyphthalonic acid (II), which is isolated as its aniline salt (III), which is then transformed to anilino-4:5-methylenedioxyphthalaldehydic acid (IV) by boiling in dry xylene and which in its turn is hydrolysed to 4:5-methylenedioxyphthalaldehydic acid, m. p. 167°.

4:5-Methylenedioxyphthalaldehydic acid (V) gives on reduction with sodium amalgam 4:5-methylenedioxyphthalide (VII), which is also obtained by decarboxylating 4:5-methylenedioxyphthalide carboxylic acid (VI), obtained by the reduction of 4:5-methylenedioxyphthalonic acid (II) by means of sodium amalgam.

5-Methoxyphthalaldehydic acid (X) has been synthesised in the following manner. 2-Methyl-4-methoxyacetophenone (VIII) (*cf.* Noller and Adams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 1893) is oxidised by means of potassium permanganate to 5-methoxyphthalonic acid (IX), which in its turn is converted into 5-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid (X) *via* the sodium bisulphite compound.

When 2:6-dimethoxynaphthalene is oxidised, 5-methoxyphthalonic acid (IX) is found as the main product and 4-methoxyphthalonic acid (XII) is formed only in minute quantities (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 695). It was, therefore, thought that it may be possible to obtain 4-methoxyphthalonic acid in better yields by the oxidation of 2:7-dimethoxynaphthalene. On the oxidation of 2:7-dimethoxynaphthalene (XI), a mixture of methoxyphthalonic acids was obtained which is converted into the corresponding methoxyphthalaldehydic acids through the bisulphite compound.

It has been observed that 4-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid (XIII), m. p. 141° , is more soluble in water and much less soluble in benzene than

5-methoxy-acid (X), m. p. 144°, and this property has been utilised for separating the two isomers in a state of purity by a careful series of fractional crystallisations from benzene and water. The constitutions of these acids (XIII) and (X), (m. p. 141° and 144° respectively), obtained from the oxidation products, are established by direct comparison with authentic specimens, synthesised by methods which leave little doubt as to their constitution (Chakravarti, *loc. cit.* p. 697; Chakravarti and Swaminathan, *loc. cit.* p. 875).

An account of the synthesis of the remaining methoxy- and methylenedioxy-*o*-aldehydocarboxylic acids is reserved for a future communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Aniline Salt of 4:5-Methylenedioxyphthalonic Acid (III).—4:5-Methylenedioxyhomophthalic acid (5 g.) was suspended in dry xylene (400 c.c.) and the mixture heated to boiling. To the boiling mixture, selenium dioxide (3.3 g.) was added and the boiling continued for 3 hours, when the homophthalic acid gradually went into solution and a deep red solution containing a black deposit of selenium was obtained. The mixture was thoroughly extracted with dilute sodium carbonate solution and the combined extracts just acidified and evaporated to dryness. The residue was then taken up in boiling water (60 c.c.), filtered from a little insoluble residue and the filtrate treated with aniline (4 c.c.). The mixture was heated for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour on the water-bath when the aniline derivative of 4:5-methylenedioxyphthalonic acid (III) separated (4 g.) The aniline derivative crystallised from alcohol in plates, m. p. 190°.

The *p*-*toluidine* derivative, prepared in a similar manner, crystallised from ethyl alcohol in leaflets, m. p. 193°. (Found: C, 66.6; H, 5.3. $C_{24}H_{22}O_4N_2$ requires C, 66.4; H, 5.1 per cent).

Anilino-4:5-methylenedioxyphthalaldehydic Acid (IV).—The aniline salt (2 g.) was suspended in dry xylene (20 c.c.) and the mixture refluxed for 1½ hours, when a clear solution resulted. On cooling, the aniline derivative of 4:5-methylenedioxyphthalaldehydic acid separated, which after repeated crystallisation from alcohol was obtained as colourless plates, m. p. 187°. (Found: C, 66.6; H, 4.0. $C_{16}H_{11}O_4N$ requires C, 66.9; H, 4.1 per cent).

4:5-Methylenedioxyphthalaldehydic Acid (V).—The aniline derivative (IV) (1.5 g.) was heated with dilute hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) on the steam-bath for 1½ hours. On cooling an acid separated in clusters of needles which, after recrystallisation from water and drying at 100°, melted at

167°. It is readily soluble in alcohol, moderately soluble in benzene and practically insoluble in petroleum ether. (Found: C, 55.5; H, 3.1. $C_9H_8O_5$ requires C, 55.7; H, 3.1 per cent).

4:5-Methylenedioxyphthalide-carboxylic Acid (VI).—The compound (I) (5 g.) was oxidised under the conditions described above and the solution of the crude phthalonic acid in water (50 c. c.) was reduced by the gradual addition of sodium amalgam (100 g., 4%). The filtered solution was acidified, when the acid (VI) separated in clusters of shining needles, m. p. 223°, yield 2 g. It was recrystallised from water. (Found: C, 53.9; H, 3.0. $C_{10}H_8O_6$ requires C, 54.1; H, 2.7 per cent).

4:5-Methylenedioxyphthalide (VII).—The acid (V) (0.3 g.), dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide solution (5%, 10 c. c.), was reduced with excess of sodium amalgam (4%, 10 g.). The aqueous solution separated from the mercury, was filtered and acidified strongly and heated on the steam-bath for 15 minutes, when, on cooling, the phthalide separated in almost theoretical yield as prismatic needles, m. p. 189° after crystallisation from water. It is sparingly soluble in benzene and almost insoluble in petroleum ether. It dissolves readily in methyl and ethyl alcohols. The phthalide was also obtained by decarboxylating acid (VI) in boiling quinoline solution with copper chromite as a catalyst. The mixed m. p. of the specimens, obtained by the two methods, remained undepressed. (Found: C, 60.5; H, 3.6. $C_9H_8O_4$ requires C, 60.6; H, 3.4 per cent).

5-Methoxyphthalaldehydic Acid (X).—To a mixture of 2-methyl-4-methoxyacetophenone (VIII) (24 g.) and potassium carbonate (12 g. in 240 c. c. water) heated on the steam-bath, a hot solution of potassium permanganate (90 g. in 900 c. c. water) was gradually added with stirring. After the addition of all the permanganate, the whole was further heated for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour on the steam-bath and filtered. The filtrate and the washings of the manganese precipitate were made just acid with hydrochloric acid and concentrated to a small volume. The hot liquid was then made alkaline with ammonia and treated with a concentrated solution of calcium chloride (48 g.) in water. The precipitated calcium salt (25 g.) was filtered, washed with water and then suspended in water. The mixture was heated to boiling, acidified with hydrochloric acid and the resulting solution cooled and extracted with ether (5 times). The ethereal extract was dried over sodium sulphate and the solvent removed. The residue was neutralised with dilute solution of sodium carbonate and evaporated to dryness. Freshly prepared sodium hydrogen sulphite solution (75 c. c. of 15%) was added to the salt and the whole evaporated to dryness on the steam-bath. The residue was further heated for one

hour at 120 in an air-oven and then twice stirred up with excess of hydrochloric acid and evaporated to dryness on the steam-bath in an open dish. This residue was then extracted twice with boiling benzene and the combined benzene extract concentrated to a small volume and allowed to remain when the acid (X) gradually separated (8 g.). It crystallised from water in beautiful silky needles, m. p. 144°. (Found: C, 59·8; H, 4·7. $C_9H_8O_4$ requires C, 60·0; H, 4·4 per cent).

Oxidation of 2:7-dimethoxynaphthalene (XI).—2:7-Dimethoxynaphthalene (prepared by methylation of 2:7-dihydroxynaphthalene with dimethyl sulphate in alkaline solution) was oxidised and the product of oxidation (a mixture of phthalonic acids) converted into the corresponding phthalaldehydic acids, under conditions similar to those described for 2:6-dimethoxynaphthalene (*cf.* Chakravarti, *loc. cit.*). The final benzene extract on cooling deposited crude 4-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid contaminated with some 5-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid (A). The whole was filtered and the residue (A) was twice crystallised from benzene and then from water when 4-methoxy acid (XIII) separated in balls of minute prismatic needles, m.p. 141°. (Found: C, 59·9; H, 4·6. Calc. for $C_9H_8O_4$: C, 60·0; H, 4·4 per cent). A mixed melting point with 4-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid previously synthesised (Chakravarti and Swaminathan *loc. cit.*) caused no depression.

The benzene mother-liquors from (A) were concentrated to a very small volume and the solid which separated was repeatedly crystallised from hot water when 5-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid (X) was obtained in beautiful long needles, m. p. 144°. (mixed m. p. with an authentic specimen previously synthesised, Chakravarti, *loc. cit.*). (Found: C, 59·8; H, 4·5. Calc. for $C_9H_8O_4$: C, 60·0; H, 4·4 per cent).

Pure 4-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid (XIII) is sparingly soluble in benzene and very easily soluble in water, while 5-methoxy acid (X) is much more soluble in benzene and less soluble in water.

During the oxidations considerable quantities of 2:7-dimethoxynaphthalene were recovered unchanged (8 g. from 20 g.) by extracting the precipitated manganese dioxide etc. with boiling acetone. This shows that probably better yields of the oxidation products could be obtained by oxidising the corresponding hydroxymethoxynaphthalenes. This point is being investigated.

Part of the work recorded in this paper was done at Annamalainagar during 1935-1936.